

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF ALCOHOLIC HEPATITIS WITH NEUROPATHY: YAKRUT VIKARA WITH ADHARANGA VATA LAKSHANAS: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Alcoholic hepatitis represents a severe inflammatory stage of ALD, characterized by hepatocellular injury, elevated liver enzymes, jaundice, and progressive hepatic dysfunction. Chronic alcohol consumption is also associated with neurological complications called alcohol-related neuropathy which is most common. Clinically, it presents as distal symmetrical motor impairment, paresthesia, muscle weakness, gait disturbances, and functional disability. In Ayurveda, liver disorders are described under the broader concept of *Yakrut Vikara*. Neurological features such as numbness, weakness, pain, and motor dysfunction of the lower limbs are described as *Adharanga Vata*. **Case Report:** A Male patient of 36 yrs suddenly developed weakness, pain, numbness in bilateral lower limb associated with swelling in B/L feet along with

yellowish discolouration in sclera and skin. Due to weakness and numbness he was unable to walk & get up from sitting position. **Methodology:** Treatment given were *Deepana-pachana*, *Nithya virechana*, *Erandamooladi Ksheera basti* initially, After *parihara kala* of *basti*, *Sarvanga abhyanga*, *Patrapinda sweda*, *Mustadi rajayapana Basti* was given. **Conclusion:** The present subject showed significant symptomatic improvement with near complete symptom resolution.

INTRODUCTION

Alcoholic hepatitis is characterized by hepatocellular injury, jaundice, deranged liver enzymes, and progressive hepatic dysfunction, often occurring in individuals with prolonged and excessive alcohol consumption. Despite advances in modern medicine, the management of alcoholic hepatitis remains challenging due to limited therapeutic options, high relapse rates, and frequent systemic complications.^[1]

Chronic alcohol consumption is also known to cause alcohol-related neuropathy, a common neurological complication resulting from the direct neurotoxic effects of alcohol, nutritional deficiencies (particularly thiamine), and metabolic disturbances. Clinically, alcoholic neuropathy manifests as distal symmetrical sensory and motor deficits, paresthesia, muscle weakness, gait disturbances, and reduced quality of life. The coexistence of hepatic and neurological involvement further complicates management and prognosis, emphasizing the need for holistic and multimodal therapeutic approaches.^[2]

Ayurveda conceptualizes liver disorders under the broad framework of *Yakrut Vikara*, wherein the liver (*Yakrut*) is considered the principal site of *Raktavaha Srotas* and a vital organ involved in metabolic transformation.^[3] Excessive intake of *Madya* (alcohol), described as *Tikshna*, *Ushna*, and *Vyavayi*, is known to vitiate *Pitta Dosha* and *Rakta Dhatu*, leading to pathological changes.^[4] Classical Ayurvedic texts describe conditions such as *Madatyaya*, *yakritodara*, *Pittaja Yakrut Vikara*, and *Raktadushti* that closely resemble the clinical features of Alcoholic hepatitis.

Prevalence of ALD is estimated at 3.5% in the general population, 26.0% among hazardous drinkers, and 55.1% among those with alcohol use disorders. Mortality varies with the disease severity with about 20% in mild forms, and between 30% and 60% in severe AH.^[1]

Neurological manifestations such as numbness, weakness, pain, and impaired motor functions of the lower limbs are described in Ayurveda under *Adharanga Vata Lakshanas*^[5], arising due to vitiation of *Vata Dosha*, often secondary to *Dhatu Kshaya*, *Avarana*, or chronic systemic disorders. Thereby these contributing to neurological deficits comparable to alcoholic neuropathy.^[6]

Ayurvedic management emphasizes *Nidana Parivarjana* (cessation of causative factors), *Shodhana* (purificatory therapies), and *Shamana* (pacificatory measures), along with

Rasayana therapy to restore tissue integrity and functional balance.^[7] Therapeutic strategies focusing on *Yakrut Uttejana*, *Pitta Shamana*, *Vata Anulomana*, and *Dhatu Poshana* have the potential to address both hepatic pathology and neurological manifestations simultaneously.

Given the limitations of conventional treatment and the growing interest in integrative medicine, documenting clinical evidence on Ayurvedic interventions in complex conditions such as Alcoholic hepatitis with neuropathy is of significant importance. The present case study aims to highlight the role of Ayurveda in the management of *Yakrut Vikara* associated with *Adharanga Vata Lakshanas*, demonstrating clinical improvement through a holistic, individualized Ayurvedic approach.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

- To evaluate the effectiveness of Ayurvedic management in a patient with Alcoholic hepatitis presenting with neuropathic symptoms, correlating clinical findings with *Yakrut Vikara* and *Adharanga Vata Lakshanas*.
- To evaluate hepatic and neurological status using clinical and Ayurvedic parameters.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

CASE REPORT

History of Present Illness

A Male patient of 36 yrs was apparently normal 1 week ago. He suddenly developed weakness, pain, Numbness in bilateral lower limb associated with swelling in B/L feet along with yellowish discolouration in sclera and skin. He also complains of loss of appetite, Nausea, mild pain in abdomen with slight distension & Mild puffiness in face. Due to weakness and numbness he was unable to walk & get up from sitting position. For these complaints, he consulted an allopathic physician where blood investigations and MRI scan was suggested. Some medicines were prescribed but symptoms did not subside. So for all these complaints he came to our hospital for better management.

History of Past Illness

No other comorbidities known

Surgical history: NIL

Occupational History

Due to stress, body pain after Field work - Alcohol consumption.

Personal History

Diet: Mixed

Bowel: Constipated, dark yellowish stools

Appetite: Reduced

Micturition: Yellowish discolouration + Increased frequency (7-8 times)

Sleep: Disturbed

Habits: Alcohol since 12 years minimum of 90 ml daily (Rum, Beer), Smoking 8 beedi per day

GENERAL EXAMINATION

- Built: Hyposthenic
- Height : 174 cm
- Weight: 54 kg
- BMI: 17.8
- Pallor: Mild +
- Icterus: +++
- Cyanosis: Absent
- Clubbing: Absent
- Lymphadenopathy: Absent
- Edema: in B/L feet- non pitting ; in periorbital region

Vitals

- Temperature : 98.6 F
- Pulse rate: 68 / min
- Respiratory Rate: 18 per minute
- Heart Rate : 68/ min
- Blood pressure : 110/70 mmhg

SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION

- Respiratory system – NAD
- Cardiovascular system- NAD

Gastrointestinal System

	Findings
Inspection	Oral Cavity : Tongue –yellowish discolouration present Halitosis: Absent Shape of Abdomen : Mild distension of Abdomen present

	Umbilicus : inverted Visible swelling : Absent Distended Veins: Absent Scars and sinuses : Absent
Palpation	Tenderness: Umbilical region, in Right hypochondriac region Organomegaly : Absent
Percussion	Shifting dullness: + Horseshoe dullness: + Fluid thrill: +
Auscultation	Bowel sounds heard

Central Nervous System Examination

HMF	Findings
Consciousness	Conscious and oriented to person, place and time
Memory	Intact
Intelligence	Intact
Hallucination / Delusion	Absent
Dysphagia & Dysarthria	Absent
Cranial nerve Examination	Normal

Motor System Examination	Findings
Muscle Bulk	Normal
Muscle tone	
Right upper limb	Normal
Left Upper Limb	Normal
Right lower limb	Hypotonic
Left lower limb	Hypotonic

Muscle Power	Right	Left
Upper limb	Normal	Normal
Lower limb	1/5	1/5

Deep tendon reflexes	Right	Left
Biceps	Normal	Normal
Triceps	Normal	Normal
Supinator	Normal	Normal
Knee	Diminished	Diminished
Ankle	Diminished	Diminished
Babinski	Normal	Normal

Sensory System- NAD

ASHTA STHANA PARIKSHA

<i>Sthana</i>	
<i>Nadi</i>	<i>Vatapitta</i>
<i>Mutra</i>	<i>Haridra mutra, Atipravrutti +</i>
<i>Mala</i>	<i>Haridra, Baddha Varcha</i>
<i>Jihwa</i>	<i>Lipta, haridratva present</i>

Shabda	Prakruta
Sparsha	Sheeta-ushnata - prakruta, shopha in paada, Mukha+
Drik	Haridra netra+
Akriti	Krishha

DASHAVIDHA PARIKSHA

Pariksha	
Prakriti	Vatapitta
Vikriti	Pitta(Pachaka, Ranjaka), Vata (Vyana, Samana, Apana), Kapha(Kledaka)
Sara	Madhyama
Samhanana	Madhyama
Satva	Madhyama
Satmya	Madhyama
Aharashakti	Abhyavaharana Shakti : Avara Jarana Shakti: Avara
Vyayamashakti	Avara
Vaya	Madhyama
Pramana	Krishha

SAMPRAPTI: (Flowchart No.1)

SAMPRAPTI GHATAKA:(Table no. 1)

Samprapti ghataka	Involved
<i>Dosha</i>	<i>Pitta(Pachaka, Ranjaka), Vata(Samana, Vyana, Apana), Kapha (Kledaka)</i>
<i>Dushya</i>	<i>Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa, Asthi, Majja</i>
<i>Agni</i>	<i>Jatharagni janya, Dhatwagni mandya janya</i>
<i>Srotas</i>	<i>Annavaaha, Rasavaaha, Raktavaaha, Udakavaaha, Swedavaaha, Asthi-Majjavaha</i>
<i>Srotodushti</i>	<i>Atipravrutti, Sanga, Vimargagamana</i>
<i>Udbhava Sthana</i>	<i>Amapakwashaya</i>
<i>Sanchara Sthana</i>	<i>Sarva Shareera</i>
<i>Vyakta Sthana</i>	<i>Twak, Netra, Mutra, Mala, Adhah Shareera</i>
<i>Adhithana</i>	<i>Sarva Shareera</i>
<i>Rogamarga</i>	<i>Abhyantara, Madhyama</i>
<i>Sadhyasadhyata</i>	<i>Kashta sadhya</i>

DIAGNOSIS: Alcoholic Hepatitis with Neuropathy.**INTERVENTION****Table no. 2: Therapeutic intervention (Panchakarma and Shamanoushadhi).**

Date	Chikitsa given	Changes observed
18/05/2025- 31/05/2025 (14 days)	<i>NABB swarasa 30ml-0-30 ml</i> <i>Arogyavardhini rasa 1-0-1A/F</i> <i>Patolakaturohinyadi Kashaya 20 ML-0-20ML</i> <i>Nithya Virechana with</i> <i>Gandharvahastadi Eranda taila 0-0-5</i> <i>ML with Hot water</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Inability to walk- 10 % better ➤ Pain, Numbness in LL- Persists ➤ Weakness in bilateral lower limb-10 % better ➤ Swelling in B/L feet – 80% reduction ➤ Yellowish Discolouration in sclera, skin, urine - 80% reduction ➤ Mild Pain in abdomen – 80 % reduction ➤ Loss of appetite -90% reduction ➤ Nausea – Subsided
1/06/2025- 8/06/2025 (8 days)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Yoga Basti-</i> <i>A- Mahatiktaka Ghrita-40 ML</i> <i>N-</i> <i>Madhu -30 mL</i> <i>Saindhava lavana- 6 gm</i> <i>Mahathiktaka Ghrita-40 ml</i> 2. <i>Arogyavardhini rasa 1-0-1 A/F</i> 3. <i>Patolakaturohinyadi Kashaya 20 ML-0-20ML</i> 4. <i>Ksheerabala 101 4 drops-0-4 drops with milk B/F</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Inability to walk- 50 % better ➤ Weakness in bilateral lower limb- 50 % better ➤ Muscle power- 3/5 in B/L LL ➤ Pain in thighs, knee joint- Reduced By 30% ➤ Numbness in LL- Reduced By 50% ➤ Swelling in B/L feet – 100% reduction ➤ Yellowish Discolouration in sclera, skin, urine - 100% reduction ➤ Mild Pain in abdomen and mild distension – 100 % reduction ➤ Appetite -100% improved
2/07/2025- 16/7/2025	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Sarvanga Abhyanga with</i> <i>Ksheerabala taila f/b Patrapinda sweda</i> 2. <i>Kala basti</i> <i>Guggulu tikthaka ghrita-40 ML</i> <i>N- Madhu- 40 ml</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Muscle power- 5/5 in B/L LL ➤ Weakness in bilateral lower limb- 100 % better ➤ Numbness in LL- Reduced By 100% ➤ Pain in thighs, knee joint- Reduced by

<p><i>Saindhava Lavana</i>- 6 gm <i>Guggulutiktaka ghrita</i> - 40 ml <i>Mustadi Kalka</i> - 20 gm <i>Mustadi Ksheera paka</i> - 350 ml <i>Avapa- Ajamamsa rasa</i>- 100 ml</p>	<p>80%</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Able to walk ➤ Get up from sitting Position- Possible ➤ LFT values -Normal ➤ CT Brain after Treatment – Normal Study
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OBSERVATION AND RESULT

MUSCLE POWER: (Table no. 3)

	BEFORE ERANDAMOOOLADI BASTI	AFTER ERANDAMOOOLADI BASTI	AFTER MUSTADI RAJAYAPANA BASTI
UPPER LIMB	NORMAL	NORMAL	NORMAL
LOWER LIMB	1/5	3/5	5/5

MUSCLE TONE: (Table no. 4)

	BEFORE TREATMENT	AFTER TREATMENT
UPPER LIMB	NORMAL	NORMAL
LOWER LIMB	HYPOTONIC	NORMAL

REFLEXES: (Table no. 5)

	BEFORE TREATMENT		AFTER TREATMENT	
	Right	Left	Right	Left
Knee Reflex	Diminished	Diminished	Normal	Normal
Ankle Reflex	Diminished	Diminished	Normal	Normal

OUTCOME & FOLLOW UP: Symptoms were reduced significantly. There is no relapse of symptoms.

TEST	RESULT	BIOLOGICAL REFERENCE RANGE	UNIT
LIVER FUNCTION TEST			
*SGOT (AST)			
SERUM ASPARTATE AMINOTRANSAMINASE (SGOT)	2687	High	Upto 40
*SGPT (ALT)			
SERUM ALANINE AMINOTRANSFERASE (SGPT)	411	High	Upto 41
*ALKALINE PHOSPHATASE			
SERUM ALKALINE PHOSPHATASE	73.0		40 - 129
*PROTEINS			
SERUM TOTAL PROTEIN	6.11	Low	6.6 - 8.7
SERUM ALBUMIN	3.97		3.9 - 5.0
SERUM GLOBULIN	2.14	Low	2.3 - 3.6
A/G RATIO	1.9		0.8 - 2.0
*BILIRUBIN (TOTAL, DIRECT, INDIRECT)			
SERUM TOTAL BILIRUBIN	8.35	High	0.3 - 1.3
SERUM DIRECT BILIRUBIN	5.36	High	< 0.3
SERUM INDIRECT BILIRUBIN	2.99	High	Upto 1.0

TEST PARAMETER	RESULT	REFERENCE RANGE
BIOCHEMISTRY		
*LIVER FUNCTION TEST (LFT)		
TOTAL BILIRUBIN	1.98 mg/dl	0 - 1 mg/dl
DIRECT BILIRUBIN	1.17 mg/dl	0 - 0.25 mg/dl
INDIRECT BILIRUBIN	0.81 mg/dl	
ASPARTATE AMINOTRANSFERASE (SGOT/AST)	48 U/L	up to 40 U/L
ALANINE AMINOTRANSFERASE (SGPT/ALT)	27 U/L	up to 40 U/L
ALKALINE PHOSPHATASE	81 IU/L	44 - 147 IU/L
TOTAL PROTEIN	9.0 g/dl	6 - 8.5 g/dl
SERUM ALBUMIN	4.9 g/dl	3.5 - 5.2 g/dl
SERUM GLOBULIN	4.1 g/dl	2.3 - 3.5 g/dl
A/G RATIO	1.2	1 - 1.5

BEFORE AND AFTER REPORTS OF LFT

History	HEADACHE	Referring Doc	MED A
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CT HEAD - UNENHANCED

FINDINGS:

- Cerebral parenchyma is normal with normal gray & white matter attenuation values.
- Cortical sulci, cisterns, cerebellar foliae & ventricles are normal.
- Brainstem and cerebellum appears normal.
- Bony calvaria is normal.
- Deviation of nasal septum noted to left with bony nasal spur
- Mucosal thickening noted in right maxillary sinus.
- Hyperpneumatization of petrous and squamous parts of bilateral temporal bones

IMPRESSION:

➤ NO SIGNIFICANT INTRACRANIAL ABNORMALITY.

 Dr. K.B. UMAMAHESHWARI

 DR. AISHWARYA S H

ABWH NO	REPORTED 10/05/2025 14:42:02
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CT SCAN

CT SCAN - BRAIN (PLAIN)
EXAMINATION

CT Scan performed on latest State-of-Art SIEMENS SOMATOM go.Top - 128 slices per 0.3 sec (384 slices per second) with DUAL ENERGY TWIN SPIRAL technology for exceptional temporal resolution, high quality imaging with minimal radiation. CORONARY ANGIOGRAM, PULMONARY, VASCULAR, Musculoskeletal and whole body imaging are integrated with AI guided 3D Reconstruction. Coronary Calcium score, Renal calculi morphology, Gout mapping, Pulmonary 3D volume, Neuro DSA, Lesion iodine mapping are now driven by AI based applications for best accuracy.

Multislice CT sections of the brain were studied from base of the skull to the vertex.

OBSERVATIONS:

Prominence of cerebral sulci, basal cisterns, cerebellar foliae and ventricular system noted.

The cerebral hemispheres and basal ganglia otherwise demonstrate normal attenuation without focal abnormality.

The cerebellar hemispheres and brain stem are otherwise unremarkable.

No obvious intracranial hemorrhage, mass effect or midline shift.

The calvarium is unremarkable. No obvious fracture.

Mucosal thickening noted in right maxillary sinus, suggestive of sinusitis.

The mastoid air cells and visualized other paranasal sinuses are clear.

IMPRESSION:

- NEUROARENCHYMAL ATROPHIC CHANGES.

Recommended: Clinical correlation.
CONCLUSION

BEFORE AND AFTER REPORTS OF CT BRAIN.

Table no. 6- USG Reports.

USG abdomen and pelvis on 15/05/2025	USG abdomen and pelvis on 17/07/2025
<p>Impression:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Mild Bilateral Pleural effusion ➤ Altered Echotexture of Liver ➤ Moderate Ascitis ➤ Minimally Distended Gall bladder 	<p>Impression</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Fatty liver Grade I ➤ No any other significant abnormality

DISCUSSION ON DISEASE

Alcoholic hepatitis is a progressive inflammatory liver disease resulting from chronic alcohol consumption and is often associated with systemic complications such as peripheral neuropathy. In the present case, ultrasonographic evaluation of the abdomen revealed altered hepatic echotexture suggestive of fatty infiltration with features of Steatohepatitis, indicating an early (Stage-I) alcoholic liver disease. This altered echotexture reflects hepatocellular injury with fat accumulation and inflammatory changes, which is consistent with the initial stage of Alcohol-induced liver damage.

In Ayurveda, this condition can be comprehensively understood under the broad concept of *Yakrut Vikara*. Acharya Bhavamishra, in *Bhavaprakasha*, has given a detailed description of *Yakrut Vikaras*. The *Yakrut* (liver) is considered the *Sthana* of *Ranjaka Pitta* and is responsible

for the proper formation of *Rakta Dhatu*. Any derangement of *Pitta* and *Rakta* directly affects the *Yakrut*, leading to *Yakrut Vikaras*.^[8]

Chronic indulgence in *Madya Sevana*, which is described as *Ushna*, *Tikshna*, *Sara*, and *Abhishyandi*, results in vitiation of *Pitta Dosha*, leading to *Drava Guna Vriddhi*, *Vata Prakopa*, and *Agni Dushti*. Along with this, the *Abhishyandi Guna* causes *Kledaka Kapha Dushti*, resulting in *Apakwa Anna Rasa* and *Ama Utpatti*. By *Ashraya–Ashrayi Bhava*, and due to the *Swabhava* of the *Nidana* consumed by the patient, *Rakta Dushti* occurs. *Yakrut* is considered the *Moola Sthana* of *Raktavaha Srotas*; therefore, when these *Nidanas* are consumed for a prolonged period, they lead to *Yakrut Vikara*, and if neglected further, progresses to *Yakrutodara*. In the present case, *Pitta Ati Pravritti* resulted in classical features such as *Peeta Vit*, *Mutra*, *Netra*, and *Twakadi*. Due to *Mala Avarodha* in both *Urdhva* and *Adha Srotas*, there was accumulation of *Kleda* in *Udara*, leading to *Udara Lakshanas*.

Peripheral neuropathy manifests clinically as numbness, tingling, pain, and weakness predominantly in the lower limbs. These features closely correspond to *Adharanga Vata Lakshanas*. Chronic *Madya Sevana* causes *Ojokshaya* and *Dhatukshaya*, i.e., improper *Poshana* of *Uttarottara Dhatus*, resulting in *Vata Prakopa*, which localizes in the *Adharanga*, leading to *Bala* and *Mamsa Kshaya*.

Hence, initially, to address *Agni Dushti* and to prevent further *Mala Sanga* and *Kleda Utpatti*, *Deepana–Pachana*, *Yakrut Uttejana*, and *Nithya Virechana* were planned, followed by *Basti Chikitsa* for *Bala Mamsa Kshaya*.

DISCUSSION ON TREATMENT

Chikitsa sutra of *Yakrut vikaras* are similar to *Yakrutodara chikitsa* mentioned by *Acharya Charaka* which includes *Snehana*, *Swedana*, *Virechana*, *Niruha basti*, *Anuvasana basti* and *Siravyadha*.^[9] In the present case, subject presented with reduced *Agni bala*, *Dourbalya*, *baddha peeta varcha*, *Peeta mutra* and *twak*, *bala mamsa kshaya*, Hence, instead of initiating immediate *Shodhana*, *Shamanoushadhis* with *Deepana-Pachana*, *Yakrut-uttejaka (tikta) dravyas* were given along with *Nithya Virechana*.^[10]

NABB swarasa.^[11] (Table no. 7)

Sl no	Name	Constituents
1	<i>Nimba</i>	Azadiractanin
2	<i>Amruta</i>	Berebrine, Cardifolioside

3	<i>Bhringaraja</i>	Ecliptol
4	<i>Bhumyamalaki</i>	Lignans, phyltetrolin

- It consists of *Katu, Tikta Rasa, Katu Vipaka, Laghu* and *Ruksha Guna Dravyas*
- Due to its *Rasa & Gunas* it does *Shoshana* of excessive *Kleda* and does *Deepana - pachana, Pitta-Rechana, Rakta Shodhana* and *Yakrut-Uttejana*
- *Bhringaraja* contains triterpenoids (echinocystic acid) which helps in arresting the progression of fibrotic changes in liver and its reversal.
- Drugs are having Anti-inflammatory, Immunomodulatory, and Hepatoprotective action.

Arogyavardhini rasa^[12]

- Main ingredient is *Katuki* which is having *Tikta rasa, Sara guna, Katu vipaka, Bhedana karma*, again it acts on *Pitta* and does *Pitta rechana* by virtue of its *Sara guna* and *Mala bhedana* by virtue of its *Bhedana karma*.
- It does *Deepana-Pachana, Malashuddhikarana, Kshudhvardhana* and is *Sarvarogaprashamani*.
- It stabilizes hepatocyte membranes and supports structural integrity of liver tissue, Neutralize oxidative stress and improve metabolic enzyme activities, enhance digestive enzyme activity and metabolic clearance of toxic metabolites, and is having Potential anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial effects.

Nithya Virechana^[13]

- In *Udara vyadhi* there is *accumulation* of *Kleda* and *Mala* within the *Srotas*, resulting in *Srotorodha* and impaired *Agni*. So *Acharya Charaka* advocates *Nithya Virechana* as a measure to eliminate morbid *Doshas* and excess *Kleda*. *Nithya virechana* was given with *Gandharvahastadi eranda taila* 0-0-5 ml daily with hot water in order to remove the *Sanchita Kleda, malas* and finally to reduce the *srotorodha* by *mala*.
- Regular mild purgation (*Nithya Virechana*) facilitates bowel regulation, enhances gut clearance, reduces intestinal and systemic fluid overload, and supports hepatic and metabolic functions, thereby preventing further disease progression and improving overall homeostasis.

Gandarvahastadi eranda taila^[14]

- Indicated in *Avrita condition, Alpa agni, Shopha, Udara*
- It Does *Anulomana* of *Vata, Balya, Brimhana*

- Ricinoleic acid in *Eranda Taila* improves cellular membrane permeability, helping phytochemicals to reach deeper tissues. The synergistic effect of Triphala and Trikatu enhances microcirculation and reduces inflammation

YOGA BASTI

Niruha- Erandamooladi ksheera basti^[15]

Anuvasana -Mahatiktaka ghrita

After attainment of proper *Agni bala*, *Erandamooladi Ksheera basti* was administered, as features of *Bala kshaya*, along with numbness and pain in both lower limbs, continued to persist. Although our *Shastras* advocate Classical *virechana karma* as the primary line of management in *Yakrut vikaras*, followed by *Basti*, in the present case *Basti* therapy was preferred due to the patient's *Avara deha bala* and inability to tolerate *virechana karma*. In order to achieve both *Rechana* and *Brimhana* simultaneously, and to facilitate the elimination of residual *Ama* and *Srotorodha*, *Erandamooladi Ksheera basti* was planned. The *Ksheera* component is described in the classics as the one possessing *Rechana*, *Preenana*, *Brimhana* etc properties, supports tissue nourishment while aiding gentle evacuation, thereby making it a suitable therapeutic choice in debilitated patients requiring both purification and restoration.^[16]

Flow Chart no. 2

Drug Action

- Picosides (Katuki), Curcumin, Tinosporin present in *Mahatiktaka ghrita* improve liver pathways
- Ricinoleic acid, Nimbidin, Azadirachtin, Withanolides -Antioxidants + neuroprotective herbs + ghee deliver nutrients to nerves

- Boeravinone- Diuretic, Improves albumin synthesis, reduces inflammation
- Berberine-like alkaloids, Flavonoids & terpenoids- Improves microcirculation, reduce oxidative stress.

Mode of action in Contemporary

- Reduces neuro-inflammation and Improves gut–nerve axis.
- Improved bowel motility → reduces neurotoxin load (produced as a result of acetaldehyde) – Decreases ROS(Reactive Oxygen Species) - decreases inflammation

Sarvanga Abhyanga with Ksheerabala taila^[17]

Flow Chart no. 3:

Drug Action

Ephedrine, pseudoephedrine, and ferulic acid, showed strong interactions with inflammation (e. with g., targets related to COX- 2, TNF- α), neurodegeneration (e. g., acetylcholinesterase), and oxidative stress. Sesame oil-antioxidants like sesamin and sesamol- modulates lipid metabolism, reducing oxidative damage.

Mode of action

Oil applied over skin penetrates into the epidermis through stratum corneum. It is transported to the systemic circulation via cutaneous circulation and lymphatics.

Increase in skin temperature causes reflective increase in sympathetic activity- Vaso dilatation - increase blood flow.

Patrapinda sweda

- It Does *Snehana, Swedana, Shulahara, Vata shamaka*
- Reduces pain, relaxes the muscles, activates the local metabolic process, increases local blood flow, and thereby increasing the absorption of Sneha through the skin.

KALA BASTI*Niruha - Mustadi Yapana Basti.*^[18]*Anuvasana - Guggulu Tiktaka Ghrita***Flow Chart no. 4****Drug Action**

- Alkaloids (notably ephedrine and related), phenolics, flavonoids- CNS-stimulating (due to ephedrine), sympathomimetic actions
- Anthraquinones (purpurin, munjistin)-Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, improves microcirculation
- Khusimol, vetiselinenol, cyclocopacamphan-12-ol, vetiverol, zizanone/epizizanone, boeravinones -suppresses inflammatory cytokines (e.g. TNF- α , IL-1 β) (in vitro/in vivo) reduces edema & leukocyte migration in animal models.
- Iridoid glycosides (picroside-I & II, kutkoside), phenolic glycosides, kutkin – Hepatoprotective.

Mode of action

- Reduction in inflammation, enhanced neurotrophic support, improved myelination, better circulation, and improved gut–brain signaling helps slow neuronal loss, promotes plasticity, and partially reverses functional deficits associated with neuro-parenchymal atrophy.

Table no. 8- Summary of treatment and the changes observed.

<i>Nidana parivarjana</i>	↓ Further <i>Doshaprakopa, Ama Utpatti, Dhatukshaya</i>	Preventing further deterioration of condition
<i>Deepana-Pachana, Yakrut-uttejaka dravyas (tikta)</i>	<i>Agni Deepana, Ama pachana, Kledaharana</i>	Gradually ➤ Appetite increased Nausea & Pain in abdomen

		reduced ➤ Yellowish discolouration reduced
<i>Nithya Virechana</i>	↓ <i>Sanchita Mala</i> in the <i>srotas</i> , <i>anulomana</i> of <i>Apana Vayu</i>	Distension in Abdomen, Swelling in Feet & Face reduced
<i>Erandamooladi Ksheera Basti</i>	<i>Srotoshodhana, Avaranahara chikitsa, Balya, Vatanulomana</i>	➤ Weakness, pain and numbness in <i>adhokaya</i> – improving ➤ Yellowish discoloration – reduced
<i>Mustadi rajayapana Basti</i>	<i>Brimhana, Rasayana</i> , ↓ <i>Bala mamsa kshaya, asthi-majjagata vata lakshana</i>	➤ Weakness, pain and numbness in <i>adhokaya</i> – improved. ➤ Muscle power 5/5 in both LL

CONCLUSION

Alcoholic hepatitis associated neuropathy can be correlated with *Yakrit Vikara* associated with *Adharanga Vata Lakshanas*, signifying hepatic pathology accompanied by neuromuscular involvement of the lower limbs. The individualized treatment approach, comprising *Nidana Parivarjana, Deepana–Pachana, Yakrut Uttejaka dravyas as shamanoushadhis*, along with *Basti* for *Vata Shamana* and *Rasayana*, resulted in marked improvement in hepatic parameters, neurological symptoms, and overall functional status. Significant reduction in symptoms such as fatigue, anorexia, jaundice, numbness, and weakness of lower limbs was observed, along with improvement in liver function tests. The integrative approach not only supports hepatic regeneration but also aids in neuroprotection and functional recovery. This case study demonstrates that a holistic Ayurvedic treatment protocol targeting the root pathology can provide safe and effective management.

REFERENCES

1. Shah NJ, Royer A, John S. Alcoholic-associated hepatitis. In: StatPearls. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK470217/>.
2. Sadowski A, Houck RC. Alcoholic neuropathy. In: StatPearls. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK499856/>.
3. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita, revised by Charaka and Dridabala with Ayurveda Dipika commentary of Chakrapanidatta, edited by Vaidya Jadavji Trikamji Acharya, Chaukambha publications, Varanasi, edition reprint 2020, Vimana Sthana 5th chapter 8th verse pg.250.

4. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita, revised by Charaka and Dridabala with Ayurveda Dipika commentary of Chakrapanidatta, edited by Vaidya Jadavji Trikamji Acharya, Chaukambha publications, Varanasi, edition reprint 2020, Chikitsa Sthana 24th chapter 31th verse pg.584.
5. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita, revised by Cha raka and Dridabala with Ayurveda Dipika commentary of Chakrapanidatta, edited by Vaidya Jadavji Trikamji Acharya, Chaukambha publications, Varanasi, edition reprint 2020, Chikitsa Sthana 28th chapter 23rd verse pg. 617.
6. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita, revised by Cha raka and Dridabala with Ayurveda Dipika commentary of Chakrapanidatta, edited by Vaidya Jadavji Trikamji Acharya, Chaukambha publications, Varanasi, edition reprint 2020, Chikitsa Sthana 28th chapter 15-18th verse pg. 617.
7. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita, revised by Cha raka and Dridabala with Ayurveda Dipika commentary of Chakrapanidatta, edited by Vaidya Jadavji Trikamji Acharya, Chaukambha publications, Varanasi, edition reprint 2020, Chikitsa Sthana 13th chapter 77th verse.
8. Bhavamishra, Bhavapraksha, Commentary by Dr. Bulusu Sitaram, Published by Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, Reprint Edition 2017, Madhyama khanda Part 3, Plihayakrit adhikara.
9. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita, revised by Charaka and Dridabala with Ayurveda Dipika commentary of Chakrapanidatta, edited by Vaidya Jadavji Trikamji Acharya, Chaukambha publications, Varanasi, edition reprint 2020, Chikitsa Sthana 13th chapter 77th verse pg. 495.
10. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita, revised by Charaka and Dridabala with Ayurveda Dipika commentary of Chakrapanidatta, edited by Vaidya Jadavji Trikamji Acharya, Chaukambha publications, Varanasi, edition reprint 2020, Chikitsa Sthana 13th chapter 95-96 verse pg. 496.
11. Sameer N Naik, Management of shakashrita kamala with special reference to viral hepatitis-An observational study. Dept of Postgraduate studied in kayachikitsa Government Ayurveda Medical College Mysuru; 2000.p.93-99.
12. Ambikadas Shashtri. Rasaratnasamucchaya. 9th edition. Chapter no. 20/87. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Publisher, 1994. P400.
13. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita, revised by Charaka and Dridabala with Ayurveda Dipika commentary of Chakrapanidatta, edited by Vaidya Jadavji Trikamji Acharya,

- Chaukambha publications, Varanasi, edition reprint 2020, Chikitsa Sthana 13th chapter 61th verse pg.495.
14. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita, revised by Charaka and Dridabala with Ayurveda Dipika commentary of Chakrapanidatta, edited by Vaidya Jadavji Trikamji Acharya, Chaukambha publications, Varanasi, edition reprint 2020, Chikitsa Sthana 13th chapter 172th verse pg.499.
 15. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita, revised by Charaka and Dridabala with Ayurveda Dipika commentary of Chakrapanidatta, edited by Vaidya Jadavji Trikamji Acharya, Chaukambha publications, Varanasi, edition reprint 2020, Siddhi Sthana 3rd chapter 38-45 verse pg.696.
 16. Vagbhata, Anna Moreshwara Kunte, Krsn Ramachandra Sastri Navre, edited by Harisastripradakara, Ashtanga Hridaya with Sarvanga Sundara commentary of Arunadatta and Ayurvedarasayana commentary of Hemadri, published by Chaukambha Orientalia Varanasi, reprint tenth 2019 edition, Sutra Sthana 14th chapter, verse 8 commentary.
 17. Sushruta, Sushruta Samhita with Nibandhasangraha commentary of Sri Dalhanacharya edited by J T Acharya, Narayan Ram Acharya published by Chaukambha Orientalia, Varanasi, 2021 edition, Chikitsa Sthana 24th chapter 30th verse.
 18. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita, revised by Charaka and Dridabala with Ayurveda Dipika commentary of Chakrapanidatta, edited by Vaidya Jadavji Trikamji Acharya, Chaukambha publications, Varanasi, edition reprint 2020, Siddhi Sthana 12th chapter 16th verse pg.731.